

HR PRACTICES IN PRIVATE SERVICE SECTOR ORGANISATIONS IN INDIA

Rishi Nagpal

S.I.E.S College of Commerce and Economics, Sion, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Today's global environment is a fiercely competitive environment in which only those organisations that have policies and practises in place to attract and retain employees who help the company combat competition and contribute to novation, innovation, and ultimate development will be able to survive. The unique knowledgeable employee is in high demand at the moment since they have specific skills and information that are required for business operations. The current research looks at how talent management strategies and initiatives are used and implemented in Mumbai's private sector banks. Representatives, i.e. workers of selected banks, are polled using a self-structured questionnaire. Various statistical tests are used to collect data on personnel and the influence of talent management programmes on the operation and functioning of selected institutions.

Key Words: Talent Management, banking, combating

INTRODUCTION

"Talent can be anything that predisposes an individual to success in a position or organisation," says Jason Lauritsen. Keep the bar high, promote from inside, mind the middle, develop realistic hiring targets and stick to them, hire a dedicated recruiter, foster culture, let go, and create checks and balances are all TM tactics for fast-growing organisations.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To investigate how employees feel about talent management.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Compound adjectives The data was acquired from 250 workers of chosen banks located in various locations of the state of Mumbai using an exploratory study methodology and a non-random selection method. The current study collects data from both primary and secondary sources, including journals, research papers, articles, websites, and newspapers. The data was evaluated and interpreted with the help of the mean and standard deviation.

ANALYSIS OF DATA AND INTERPRETATION

The first step in the analytic process is to examine the demographic factors connected to the study's selected respondents, as demographic data indicates if the study's respondents are

representative of the population under examination. The various demographics utilised to collect information about respondents are as follows: -

Demographic frequency tables: -

1. Gender

The gender of employee plays very important role in concerning and taking the things related to job and other societal values and beliefs which affects the various behavioral traits. Thus, the study of demographic details starts with gender. Male and female has different perspectives about same phenomenon thus study of this component is essential.

Table 1: Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	160	64.0	64.0	64.0
Female	90	36.0	36.0	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Source: Data Analysis

The variation in gender believing TM practises is shown in table 1 of gender. The majority of the sample population was male and believed in the TM programme.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.748
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1173.943
	Df	254
	Sig.	.000

Source: Data Analysis

Discussion and Interpretation: - The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy was utilised, and the KMO value of .748 was higher than the minimal threshold of 0.6, indicating that the sample was sufficient for factor analysis. Principal Component Analysis with Varimax Rotation was used to identify three elements. The three variables accounted for 65.273 percent of the total variation. The factor loadings bigger than 0.50 were kept thanks to the Varimax rotation findings.

After determining that the sample size is appropriate for the study, factor analysis is used to identify the elements that make up a representative variable that affect, support, and act as a requirement for talent management.

Discussion and Interpretation:

This factor is loaded with four statements, with a 17.342 percent explained variance and a reliability of .612. The immediate supervisor assign responsibilities to their supervisor, there

is a lot of room for career development in the current position, the immediate supervisor discusses further career development, and the company provides support and resources for development.

This component was ranked second most important by the respondents, as it explained 43.234 percent of variation and had a reliability of .651. Medical insurance, business savings plan, retirement plan, and holiday entertainment are all areas where employees are satisfied with their pay and perks.

According to the findings, respondents deemed this component to be the most essential, with the maximum explained variance of 50.235 percent and a reliability of .712. Working in a group is beneficial. Immediate supervisor encourages teamwork, we discuss personal goals with coworkers, we work efficiently as a team inside the department, and we look for ways to collaborate proactively within the department.

FINDING OF STUDY

The data analysis yields specific outcomes, which are described as the study's primary findings and are The majority of the respondents are men between the ages of 23 and 30. They are being recognised for the talent management strategies that their company employs. Her supervisor has also introduced them to the talent management programme. Employee satisfaction with wage and perks, according to the majority of respondents.

CONCLUSION

The current study looked at the elements that influence talent management practises among private bank personnel. An exploratory cum descriptive study was conducted for this purpose. According to the findings, talent management strategies are extremely beneficial to customers and employees. To reach your objectives, you must exercise talent management. Employees at private banks are happy with the policies and advantages they receive. Employees can attain their full potential with the support of talent management practises. The focus of talent management methods is not solely on technology solutions. Talent management strategies provide a number of advantages for improving performance. According to the findings of this study, talent management strategies are advantageous to both individuals and organisations.

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